

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

EVALUATION OF FERTILITY OF GLEYSOL-YELLOW SOILS OF THE LANKARAN REGION OF AZERBAIJAN ACCORDING TO MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES ON THE BASIS OF SPECTRAL METHODS

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, space technologies and also various data-dimension systems are used for studying properties of soils in the field and laboratory. Using spectrophotometric methods, remote sensing of soils is notable for its actuality. Soils are differed according to their structure aggregate, erosion, salinity, physical-chemical properties and also their spectral indicators are various too. Using remote sensing of soils, analyzing of ecological factors of fertility in comparative disposition, on the basis of formation of their optimum fertility parameters, objective estimation of great importance.

Keywords: space technologies, ecological factors, humus quantity, agriculture, podzolic-gleysol yellow soils, chemical and water-physical analysis, morphogenetic feature, non-eroded yellow gleysol soils.

INTRODUCTION

Soils are differed according to their physical-chemical properties, so they have different spectral reflectance properties. Light soils in mechanical structure are differed incisively from heavy soils in mechanical structure for their spectral reflectance properties. Various types and subtypes of soils are different for their physical-chemical properties and also their colors. One of the main morphological outer indications of soils is considered its color. Fertility potential of soil and visual studying of its color are of great importance for processors who are engaged in modern farming economy. In the past, people in agriculture evaluated the fertility of soil for its outer indications, especially its color. The color of the soil is a significant indicator that defines its type. Various soil types characterized with various humus quantity have different spectral reflectance properties. For example, a large amount of humus-one of the main fertility indicators, make the soil dark black. In recent years 400-750 nm (nanometer) wave length in visible light spectrum is used for differentiating color indications of soils. Podzolic-gleysol yellow soils are thriven in foothills and lowlands of the Lankaran region on fluvial illuvial sediments. Soil formation happens basically as a result of surplus humidity. The structure of soil cover in the land is characterized according to its complexity. Investigated area surrounds foothills and lowlands and has a humid subtropical climate. The

quantity of common radiation is 120-125 kcal/cm², the sum of active temperature is (>10°C) 3880-4500°C. Average annual temperature is 14,2 14,5°C, the quantity of annual rain is 1200-1500 mm in low mountain and foothills (the villages of Mamusta, Siyavar, Hirkan), sometimes it becomes 1800 m (in Mamusta and Siyavar). Annual humidity indicator is above 0,45 (Md). Annual relative humidity is 100-150%. The quantity of evaporation during the year is 900 mm.

OBJECTIVES AND METHODS

The research was carried out in slowly permeable heavy textured yellow gleysol soils of the Lankaran region during 2010-2013s. In Subsidiary Experience Agriculture of Lankaran Branch tea and citrus plants of Azerbaijan Scientific Research Institute of Horticulture and Subtropical Plants, non-eroded and moderately eroded podzolic-gleysol yellow soils under tea plantation, were chosen as an investigation object. In recent years, actuality of researches is determined as a result of intensive utilization of irrigated soils, degradation of soils, reduction of fertility, mainly water-physical properties and also changing of their colors and necessity of preventing of these processes.

In the area, during researches, characteristic areas are chosen, their morphogenetic layers and soil profile description are determined. Chemical and water-physical analysis is carried out according to common accepted methodics. Physical-chemical analysis methods

of spectral properties of soils are carried out with spectrophotometric CF-18 and photocolometric methods. The temperature of the soils is determined by the distancing M-54-1 apparatus. Aerovisual deciphering of soil cover is based on distinction and selection of outer view of soils, according to their natural, geometric and color indications. Peculiarities of mezo and microrelief are studied according to their form, measure and direction.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

In summer artificial irrigation is used widely with purpose of lasting aridity. These changes under the influence of irrigation, display themselves in morphological profile of soils. The morphological structure of non-eroded yellow gleysol soils is shown in the description of soil cut 1 (table 1). Little differences observed in it, coordinate only with ecological conditions, it doesn't show amendments of species diversity of soil. It is shown distinctly from the cutting descriptions, the soil structure was changed after deforestation and nutlike structure typical for forest soils is not shown here. The following morphological indicators are typical for profile of investigated soils. 0-18 cm A layer of these soils is in grayish-yellow color (straw). Sometimes density of A layer becomes 15 cm. The color of soils lightens along the profile towards the lower layers and straw-yellow color is dominated. The stains of yellowish iron oxides are held in deep layers and it is certain sign of existence of forest cover in this area in the past. In illuvial A horizon whitish grey and pointy spots emerge. It usually happens during irrigation erosion. That's why, observations on color and separate color shades in horizons of non-eroded and moderately eroded podzolic-gleysol yellow soils gives enough information for getting to know essence of processes happening in the soil and origin of soils.

Spectral reflectance properties of soils depend on the percentage of particles of different size in it, so its granulometric composition (Table 1).

Cutting-1.A. 0-18 cm- grayish-yellow (relatively dark), heavy clayey, gleysol humus layer, ball-like nut-like structural, compacted, molten spots are much more..

A₂ 18-40 cm- whitish-grayish colored, clod-like structural, compacted, molten stained, is not boiled in HCL.

B₁ 40-65 cm- bright yellow rust-colored, heavy clayey, debris, small rootlets, unstructured, more compacted, yellow stained, humid, gradual transition, is not boiled in HCL.

B₂ 65-75 cm- rust-colored, heavy clayey, gleysol, molten small rootlet, unstructured, yellowish stained, compact, clear transition, is not boiled in HCL.

B/C 75-105 cm- light yellow brown, medium loam, unstructured rocks, humid, clear transition, is not boiled in HCL.

The morphological symptoms of moderately eroded irrigating gleysol yellow soils are shown in soil cut 2 drilled in the northwestern part of the village of Mamusta. In the area the most typical feature of soil profile is molten spots. It is explained with purpose of formation of bluish tone in separate horizons of soil in the lowest oxidation rate of iron. The diversity of bioclimatic zones in southeastern slopes of the Talysh mountains caused motley of soil cover in investigated area. Various investigators show it in their surveys [9, 1]. They defined that, the conjugation of humidity along the profile in the soil causes changing of the direction of the light rays falling on the surface of soil particles and it caused decrement of reflection coefficients of soils. Integral reflection coefficients in the soils have dependence on easily soluble iron combinations in soil solution. Specification of soil colors on the basis of results is achieved [9].

Table 1.

Mechanical structure of irrigating gleysol-yellow soils (only in dry soils)

Number of cutting	Depth, cm	Hygrosopic moisture, %	Dimension of fractions (mm), quantity(%)						Physical silt <0,01
			1,00-0,25 Sand	0,25-0,05 Fine sand	0,05-0,01 Large dust	0,01-0,005 Average dust	0,005-0,001 Fine dust	<0,001 Silt	
Non-eroded									
1	0-18	6,30	4,26	17,80	28,60	9,60	24,00	17,80	50,46
	18-40	7,60	4,70	19,30	25,00	9,50	22,60	20,85	52,60
	40-65	5,50	5,0	35,60	19,00	5,15	13,10	22,60	40,30
	65-75	5,80	3,30	39,50	25,30	3,80	11,20	18,50	34,00
	75-105	5,20	5,4	26,40	30,40	7,50	12,50	18,80	28,00
Moderately eroded									
2	0-10	4,30	0,75	16,75	32,40	4,05	27,60	21,30	48,40
	10-23	5,20	0,55	17,40	29,80	3,60	24,00	22,40	50,00
	23-43	4,40	2,60	38,50	35,10	4,50	15,45	22,15	37,25
	43-70	5,40	3,10	27,80	26,10	7,30	12,00	17,50	26,00

Cutting 2. A₂ 0-10 cm light grayish, molten stained, unstructured, compacted, heavy clayey, scattered ball-like, small stone chippings, roots, lots of rootlets, cracks, damp, soft, clear transition, is not boiled in HCL.

B₁ 10-23 cm-whitish-grayish, molten stained, gleysol rust-colored, medium loam, small clod-like ball-like, unstructured, grass rootlets, dry, little peeps, clear transition, is not boiled in HCL.

B₂ 23-43 cm light-yellowish rust-colored, small clod (is plucked of), lots of gravel, debris, stones, structure is not chosen, slightly damp, is not boiled in HCL.

B/C 43-70 cm rust-colored, gleysol, molten, unstructured, more compacted, is not boiled in HCL.

The natural condition of irrigating podzolic-gleysol-yellow soils were subjected to anthropogenic changes a lot. In some places, during surplus irrigation, as a result of irrigation erosion groundwater rises to surface and it creates serious problems.

Deforestation, replacement of natural landscape with agro landscapes, unequal accommodation of productive forces in area formation, expansion of village settlements by draining of marshes, influence of climatic changes on agricultural systems and some other factors caused the changing of initial ecological outer morphological parameters of soil [1, 8]. That's why, morphogenetic and agrochemical ecoethic problems of these soils are much more strained in comparison with yellow-podzolic soils. In cutting 1 spectrophotometric description shows distinctly that, soil cover of the area is dense and erosion process isn't observed here. But they are often subjected to seasonal superficial humidity. Gley formation process is observed in upper A and AB horizons. Genetic layers are differed according to

their color, structure, compacted and other morphological symptoms. Lightening of illuvial A₂ horizon and solidification of alluvial B horizon are explained by increasing the quantity of iron oxides. The results show that, soils of the area include in gleysol podzolic-yellow soils subtypes. In investigated area, soils including this subtype spread in podzolic-gleysol yellow soils and on the surface of young low terraces, relatively in small areas. Gleyed layers and even humus layers are characterized by high conjugation acidity. At present, these soils are used under tea plantations and are irrigated intensively.

It is shown in spectrophotometric description of cutting 2, abrupt changes happen in morphogenetic feature of moderately eroded soils. Soil profile reduced, its structure shattered, colloid fractions in mechanical structure were washed and its color lightened. Analysis results of observed distinctions in morphological symptoms prove too (Table 1). Soils are divided into dark (grey-yellowish) and light (brown-yellowish) subtypes according to thickness of humus horizon and forms of erosion. Weakly ensuring with humus along the profile, increase to the maximum extent the integral reflective capacity of light (brownish-yellowish) soil (picture 1). It is shown in picture 1 that, there is a b inversely proportional dependence between spectral reflection coefficient and humus in the soil.

It shows itself distinctly in 72-105 cm layer of soil in which the quantity of humus is 0,80%. Its integrated reflection coefficient is 32,5%. It is defined that, abundance of thickness of humus horizon reduces its integrated reflection coefficient, on the contrary in lower layers increases. That's why, agro ecological demands of plants should be conserved during the preparation of soils for planting.

Pic. 1. Spectral reflectance curves in unwashed and moderately washed yellow-gleysol soils (mkm)

Bluish color in the profile of cutting 1 and 2 proves vastly ensuring with surplus humidity. But in high humidity condition (cutting 2), as a result of etching in initial minerals of soils, decomposition happens incisively and that's why yellow-gleysol soils are heavy textured. As a result of natural and anthropogenic factors and etching, especially under the influence of etching crust arising in humid climate condition, volcanic rocks with iron and manganese combinations are covered with brownish and red crust. As it is shown in Table 1 that, in moderately washed soils the most quantity of physical clay is 50,00% in 10-23 cm layer. In upper layers of these soils podzolization occurs partially, but in illuvial layer podzolization is not selected. As a result of washing of clay minerals to the lower layers along the profile during high rainfall, illuvial layer is arisen that is not satisfactory in physical-chemical aspect. This layer derives interference to the leaking of irrigation and rainfall water to the lower layers of soil, and gleying process in bluish color happens in "B" layer of soil profile. Intensity of gleying is also explained by the impact of groundwater. The main reason of it, is transformation of trivalent iron oxide in soil to divalent iron oxide. In summer, after leaking surplus water from soil profile, soil evaporates and divalent iron oxide overturns trivalent iron oxide. Therefore, trivalent iron oxide is precipitated like membrane, spots and other bigger crystals in soil layers, various porosities and on particles. Solidification of illuvial "B" horizon abundant with iron oxides signifies. It is determined that, spectral reflection coefficient in unwashed soils by genetic layers. increased in comparison with moderately washed soils, at the same time, by accruing wavelength, its spectral reflection also increases. Distinction of silt fractions (<0,001 mm) in the upper layers of soil profile from moderately eroded soils in comparison with non-eroded soils according to color indications, coheres with washing process depending on the relief of the area. The least water -stable microaggregates (less than 0,25 mm) is also observed in areas under tea plantations. The quantity of bluff silt (0,001mm) and small dust particles prove it (Table 1).

Agrochemical indicators authenticate some characteristic signs in morphological description of irrigating gleysol-yellow soils. The result of analysis. shows that, in comparison with non-eroded soils, in upper layers of moderately eroded soils, humus 0,80-1,55%, total nitrogen 0,066-0,089%, assimilated nitrogen 14,52-15,10 mg/kg, nitrate 1,10-1,80 mg/kg, total phosphorus 0,10-0,07%, soluble phosphorus in 0,2 n HCL 28,60-19,57 mg/kg, total potassium 0,90-1,45%, exchanged potassium 55,00-63,60 mg/kg abates (pic.2 and table 2). Reduction of humus and organic residues in washed soils results in violation of soil structure and decrement of water-stable aggregates (more than 0,25 mm). Increasing of aggregate particles (less than 0,25 mm) in eroded soils show pollination of the structure as a result of washing process. Washed gleysol-yellow soils in comparison with podzolic-yellow soils have high absorptive capacity. In contrast to unwashed type of erosion, in upper layers of relatively moderately washed type, the sum of the absorbing bases reduced within

7,98-11,80 mg/ekv in 100 g soil. The sum of the absorbing bases (in 100 g soil) in planting layer of this area is 21,24-26,53 mg/ekv. Calcium cation is dominated among absorbed cations. So, for spectral reflectance properties, magnesium cation is the second and absorbed hydrogen is in the third place. That, there is an inversely proportional dependence among spectral reflectance properties and bases in the soil. Volumetric weight-one of the main physical indications of soil, worsen its physical properties during erosion process in investigated areas. In comparison with non-eroded type in the upper layers of moderately eroded soils, volume, special mass and porosity increases. In foothills and lowlands yellow gleysol soils differ from one another for their morphological outer color indications, physical-chemical properties, thickness of fertility layer and also the rate of gleying, so they have various spectral reflectance properties.

The typical factor in the main properties of investigated yellow gleysol soils is high humidity in autumn - winter, and aridity in summer. Long-lasting rain, heavy downpour which is typical for the region and also arid climate condition not only influence the dynamics of soil properties, but also cause changing of their color one of the main morphological outer features. One of the morphological peculiarities of yellow-gleysol soils is the superiority of red, orange or yellow colors throughout the entire soil profile (depending on density of trivalent iron oxide in soil). Sometimes, the upper layer becomes yellowish, in lower than 20-30 cm layers soil is relatively dark, grey-yellowish. In lower than 30-35 cm layer it is grey or brownish-yellowish color. The color of horizon B-transition layer, (density is 40-70 cm) is yellowish and brownish-yellowish. In horizon CD layers (in depth>70 cm), the iron rust-colored stains consisting of diluvial clayey are found.

Recent research has determined that, podzolization process is not observed in podzolic-gleysol yellow soils under tea plantations. They have an effect on spectral properties of physical, chemical and mechanical contents of soils[1, 8]. Results of experiments by using distance measuring equipment show that, spectral reflectance properties change depending on its fertility indicators. Many explorers have shown various spectral reflectance properties of soil. It is known that, basis of each substance and also color of the soil arranges its absorption and reflectance of electromagnetic waves. Soils reflecting intensively the light are in light color. The soil color depends on wavelengths and color saturation depends on ratios of reflecting waves. Light objects with high saturation are bright. For example, objects with red color saturation are accepted as bright red and so on [2, 3]. Various conditions of soil formation process create variety of light-absorbing complex. On the basis of these processes in every soil type specific light-absorbing and reflectance properties arise [4, 8]. Humus is a special form of organic substances, paints the upper layer of soil profile and it is inseparable content of soil. Fertility indications of soil cohere with its humic substances. Humus as an integral indicator of soil fertility shows the peculiarities of soils. Outer morphological properties and humic horizons (A+AB) of soil connect with factors of humus (humidity regime,

aeration, granulometric content, microbiological activity, pH and others) and it creates favorable agro-ecological conditions for most agricultural plants in these parts of soils. Humus influences the plants directly and regulates growth and development of plants. There are curves (graphic) in pic.2 for describing distribution of humus, common nitrogen and absorbing bases by quantity along the profile visually. It is shown in picture 2 that, incisive decrement of humus to 25-30 cm depth in moderately washed soils is observed and humus and nitrogen are negligible.

The color of soil depends on combination of soil too. Humus substances and manganese make the soil dark (grey and black). Silica oxides (SiO_2) Ca and Mg carbonates, easily soluble salt, clayey minerals and aluminum hydroxide make the soil light white or light grey. Trivalent iron oxides depending on their density in soils make it light reddish or brownish color. Divalent iron oxides paint the soil in violet colors. Combination of various integrations makes the soil the most various color. Simultaneously, the color of soil is shaped by its physical properties (spectral weight, volume weight, porosity) and also natural humidity.

Pic 2. Some chemical indicators of gleysol-yellow soils

But in color indications of structure elements of any soil horizon, humus, iron oxides, silica acid and lime are of great importance. For instance, in transition zone from washed gleysol-yellow soils of investigated area to swampy lands, in separate horizons, vivanite $[\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ arising in the lowest oxide rate of iron is observed and it creates greenish-blue shade in the soil.

From the outer morphological point of view, Silicon (IV) oxide or silica tetrahedron (SiO_2) calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) and kaolinite -the main combination of clay $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) make the soil white and whitish. In most cases, well soluble salt which soluble capacity is more than 1 q (Na, K and ammonium salt) create whitish color too. Sometimes, in farmer economy deviant using of dehydrated gypsum or burnt gypsum (CaSO_4) and H_2O cause whitish spots and shades in soil. So that, colors are various in the soil and visual

sphere of eye apparatus does not have an ability of selection colors. Especially, in rehabilitating soils, natural genetic layers of soil have collapsed and natural morphogenetic layers have not formed yet and it makes impossible to determine the color of the soil.

In order to overcome these shortcomings, 400-750 nm wavelength of visible spectrum can be used [6]. Depending on agromeliorative methods, irrigation and fertilization in investigated area agrochemical properties of soils change in (Table 2). The quantity of humus in non-eroded soils of this area change 1,80-3,35%. Integrated reflection coefficient is 31,0-41,2%. So majority of humus in soil abates its integral reflectance factor and when humus drops off, it becomes vice versa. It shows its influence incisively in eroded soils. So that, the quantity of humus in washed soil is less (0-50-1,80%) and the maximum integrated reflection coefficient is here.

Table 2.

The main agrochemical indicators of washed yellow-gleysol soils (only in dry soils)

Number of cutting	Depth, cm	Humus	Nitrogen				Phosphorus		Potassium		In PH-water solution	In PH salt solution
			Common nitrogen, %	Absorbed ammonia N/NH ₃ , mg/kg	Water-soluble N/NH ₃ , mg/kg	Nitrate (N/NO ₃ , mg/kg)	Common, %	Soluble in 0,2 n HCl	Common, %	Exchanged, mg/kg		
Non-eroded												
1.	0-15	3,35	0,172	34,30	13,84	9,10	0,17	92,72	2,80	160,80	5,5	3,7
	15-35	2,40	0,124	27,84	12,30	6,10	0,16	66,00	2,25	140,30	5,7	3,9
	35-51	1,70	0,090	21,50	6,60	5,60	0,14	41,25	2,70	140,45	5,9	4,0
	51-72	1,50	0,055	11,20	6,00	2,50	0,12	31,23	2,88	113,60	5,9	4,2
	72-105	1,80	0,025	8,85	5,25	1,60	0,09	24,65	2,60	110,30	6,1	4,5
Moderately eroded												
2.	0-10	1,80	0,083	19,20	6,33	7,30	0,10	73,15	1,35	97,20	5,8	6,9
	10-23	1,60	0,058	13,32	5,30	5,00	0,06	37,40	1,35	85,40	6,0	7,0
	23-43	1,65	0,048	16,04	3,15	3,63	0,07	29,62	1,83	79,33	6,0	7,1
	43-70	0,50	0,019	11,72	3,50	1,43	0,06	23,10	2,10	63,85	5,8	6,7

CONCLUSION

Researches show that, the following general and distinctive aspects are determined for spectral properties of non-eroded and moderately eroded soils. In non-eroded soils, easy observation of deduction of profile into genetic layers (unwashed soil); grayish yellow color in upper layers and dark (grey) color in the middle part of profile are determined. Violet color in moderately washed soils; minority of humus layer; claying in high quality and exceeding of silt fractions in the middle part of profile; non-equal distribution of iron, silica and other oxides along the profile; saturating of soils with salt have been observed. The following agro technical, agrochemical and agro-ameliorative events are recommended for improvement of their outer morphological indications (color, structure, mechanical content) by optimization of ecological parameters of moderately washed heavy clayey yellow-podzolic soils: - Restoration of natural landscapes; expansion of soil conservation forests; restoration of collector-drainage system for maintaining groundwater at optimal levels in poor-drainage areas; -plowing or softening of compacted "B" layer of soil once every 3 years; -prevention of deviant irrigation in tea planting areas taking into account rusty color, molten stained, unstructured, too compacted, 30-65 cm thickness of "B" clayey layer should be carried out. For creation of a balance of nutrients in moderately eroded soils and for increasing microbiological activity, the quantity of mineral and organic fertilizers must be optimized: for that purpose, in tea plantations every year (to 15 years or much more) 250-300 kg/ha physiological acidic fertilizer - (NH₄)₂SO₄ must be applied. Phosphorus must be applied 200 kg/ha in a year during 10 years, but potassium should be applied 150 kg/ha every year in an impressive substance form. -It is possible to determine the color of the soil by using spectral reflectance curves. -Evalua-

tion of soils for quality by remote sensing of soils, compiling of soil ecological maps enable the implementation of map correction matters and others.

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ЕКОЛОГІЧНІ ПІДХОДИ У ВИРОЩУВАННІ КУКУРУДЗИ РОЗЛУСНОЇ В УМОВАХ ПІВНІЧНОГО СТЕПУ УКРАЇНИ

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ECOLOGICAL APPROACHES IN CULTIVATION OF POPCORN MAIZE IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE NORTHERN STEPPE OF UKRAINE

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АНОТАЦІЯ

Представлено результати польових досліджень визначення впливу біопрепаратів азотфіксуючих та фосформобілізуючих бактерій на ріст, розвиток та врожайність кукурудзи розлусної сорту Шанс на чорноземі звичайному в умовах північно-центральної помірно посушливої підзони степової північної зони України (Луганська область). Визначено можливість збільшення врожайності за рахунок окремого та сумісного внесення біопрепарату азотфіксаторів Азотофіт-Р та біопрепарату фосформобілізуючих бактерій ФМБ. Задля отримання максимального урожаю зерна на рівні 15,6 ц/га рекомендовано застосування фону N45P30 та інокуляція насіння комплексом біопрепаратів Азотофіт-Р+ФМБ в день посіву препаратом 0,8 л/т насіння.

ABSTRACT

The results of field research on determining the effect of biological preparations of nitrogen-fixing and phosphorus-mobilizing bacteria on the growth, development and yield of Shans open-leaved corn on ordinary chernozem in the conditions of the north-central moderately arid subzone of the steppe northern zone of Ukraine (Luhansk region) are presented. The possibility of increasing the yield due to the separate and simultaneous application of the nitrogen-fixing biopreparation Azotophyt-R and the biopreparation of phosphorus-mobilizing bacteria FMB was determined. In order to obtain the maximum grain yield at the level of 15.6 c/ha, it is recommended to use the N45P30 background and inoculate seeds with a complex of biological preparations Azotophyt-R+FMB on the day of sowing with a preparation of 0.8 l/t of seeds.

Ключові слова: Сорти кукурудзи, розлусна кукурудза, біопрепарати азотфіксуючих і фосформобілізуючих бактерій, морфометричні показники рослин, урожайність зерна.

Keywords: Varieties of corn, open corn, biological preparations of nitrogen-fixing and phosphorus-mobilizing bacteria, morphometric indicators of plants, grain yield.

Сьогодні в Україні, як і у світі, є значний попит на якісну сировину харчової кукурудзи. Останні десятиріччя значного попиту набув й такий підвид харчової кукурудзи як кукурудза розлусна – *Zea mays everta Sturt.*

Особливо цінною вважається продукція харчової кукурудзи яка отримана з використанням екологічно безпечних технологій. Результати багаторічних досліджень показують, що перспективним шляхом отримання екологічно безпечної продукції із необхідним рівнем енергетичної та економічної ефективності технологій можна досягнути використовуючи біопрепарати азотфіксуючих та фосформобілізуючих бактерій, що надає можливість знизити норми внесення мінеральних добрив. Це стає можливим за рахунок того, що бактерії біопрепара-

тів здатні біологічно фіксувати азот та перетворювати важкодоступні для рослин фосфоровмісні сполуки ґрунту у легко доступні та дещо покривають потребу рослин у цих поживних елементах.

Багато науковців мають підтверджуючі дані тому, що біологічна фіксація азоту є одним із найважливіших процесів трансформації атмосферного азоту в компоненти біосфери. Так, у балансі в природі біологічний азот становить до 30% в надходженні і до 45–50% у відновленні родючості ґрунтів. За значимістю процес біологічної фіксації та перетворення на доступні для рослин форми азоту дорівнюють фотосинтезу [7, с. 656–678].

Застосування бактерій у біопрепаратах азотфіксуючих та фосформобілізуючих бактерій покращує азотне та фосфорне живлення, одночасно стимулюючи утворення фізіологічно активних речовин